

Supplementary Material

S1 MORDRED sectors

Sector number	Sector description
1	Agriculture, food, beverages
2	Non-energy use of biomass
3	Fossil fuels used for energy
4	Mining
5	Industry not elsewhere classified
6	Recycling industry
7	Services not elsewhere classified
8	Non-energy use of fossil fuels
9	Chemical industry
10	Biomass used for energy
11	Manufacturing
12	Fossil fuel-based electricity
13	Nuclear electricity
14	Hydroelectricity
15	Wind based electricity
16	Biomass and waste based electricity
17	Solar PV electricity
18	Solar thermal electricity
19	Tide, wave and ocean based electricity
20	Geothermal electricity
21	Transport
22	Education
23	Health
24	Waste industry
25	Waste ,recycling' (biogasification & composting) industry

Table 1: Overview of the sectors represented in MORDRED. Source: <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED/blob/main/Sectors.md>

S2 Scenario parametrization

Model variable	GG	DG
<i>Labor productivity</i>	Global average productivity increases to 1.5 times the productivity levels of high-income countries in 2019.	Global average productivity increases to the productivity levels of high-income countries in 2019.
<i>Process efficiency coefficient in the A matrix</i>	Constant energy efficiency improvements through technological progress are assumed to be offset by falling labor intensity. In sector 1 a factor of 1.1 is applied due to an assumed link between higher productivity and higher energy intensity. Energy intensity declines by 30% due to the electrification of industrial processes which reach higher levels than in the DG scenario.	Process efficiency is assumed to improve compared to a GG scenario due to higher labor intensities across sectors (10% reduction in sector 1, 20% reduction in the remaining sectors). The additional labor is assumed to be employed to develop energy saving processes and/or perform physical work that allows to replace part of the required non-human energy inputs. Efficiency intensity declines by 50% due to the electrification of industrial processes.
<i>A matrix sector 11</i>	Constant.	Inputs from sector 11 decrease by 20% for sector 1, reflecting decreased fertilizer use.
<i>Energy technologies</i>	Greening (complete replacement of nuclear and fossil energy), Electrification (reduction of non-electricity inputs by 40%); non-electric greening: replacement of 50% of inputs from sector 3 with sector 10.	Greening (complete replacement of nuclear & fossil energy to 2100), Electrification (reduction of non-electricity inputs by 25%); non-electric greening: replacement of 50% of inputs from sector 3 with sector 10.
<i>Target consumption vector of governments, GFCF and households</i>	Greening, replacement, electrification, shift from fossil to biomass to the same degree as the industrial processes. The demand for food products was adjusted in the consumption vector of the poorest household type.	Greening, replacement, electrification, shift from fossil to biomass to the same degree as the industrial processes. The demand for food products was adjusted in the consumption vector of the poorest household type.
<i>Land intensity of agriculture & forestry</i>	Intensity decreases to 0.2, 0.4 and 0.7 of 2019 values for agricultural, forest and other land, respectively .	Intensity decreases to 0.2, 0.4 and 0.7 of 2019 values for agricultural, forest and other land, respectively. Additionally: land intensity declines for agricultural and other land due to diet change and land intensity increase due to organic farming factor. The plant-based diet factor is 0.65, the organic agriculture factor is 1.31.
<i>Land intensity of energy generation</i>	30% improvement for non-biomass energy, biomass increases by the average increase of agricultural and forest land, i.e. 0.3.	30% improvement for non-biomass energy, biomass increases by the average increase of agricultural and forest land. The organic agriculture factor is also applied here and increases land intensity.
<i>Greenhouse gas emission intensity of N2O and CH4</i>	Constant as there are weak incentives to reduce intensity in the absence of a global stringent emission trading system for N2O and CH4 emissions.	Decrease due to organic agricultural practices and diet changes. The introduction of organic agriculture is reflected through a decrease in N2O intensity of 80% in the food sector. The effects of a plant-based diet are

		reflected by a reduction of current CH ₄ intensity in the food sector by 71%.
<i>N und P pollution intensity of agriculture</i>	Constant as the tendency to increase intensity due to productivity growth is assumed to offset the tendency to decrease intensity due to technology improvements.	Changes in agricultural practices, notably the shift to organic agriculture, are assumed to lead to strong decreases in N & P pollution intensity, represented through a decrease of 80%.
<i>Industrial water intensity</i>	Green water intensity decreases while blue water consumption intensity increases due to intensification of agriculture. It is assumed that 20% of green water is substituted by blue water.	
<i>Household water intensity</i>	Behavioral changes are assumed to lead to a moderate 20% decline in household blue water consumption intensity.	
<i>Consumption growth rate</i>	Consumption rates calculated according to consumption targets: the per capita consumption of classes in the center doubles until 2100; classes in the semiperiphery consume what the respective classes in the center consumed in 2019; classes in the periphery consume 0.75 times what the respective classes in the center consumed in 2019.	Global convergence to a target level of 9000 € in 2035. Consumption is given in 2019-€.
<i>Convergence</i>	Moderate convergence to a maximum consumption ratio of 10:1 between the richest and the poorest class in 2100.	Strong and fast convergence to zero consumption inequality in 2035.
<i>Capital intensity</i>	Increases by 1.5%.	Constant.
<i>Annual working hours</i>	2080 hours.	
<i>Maximum participation rate</i>	0.9	
<i>Resources</i>	High resource availability (sum of coal, oil and gas resources: 495390 EJ).	
<i>Extraction costs</i>	Exponential curve, very favorable cost curve.	
<i>Land allocation</i>	Land demand for subsistence agriculture has lower priority than land demand for monetized economic processes within the global economy.	Land demand for subsistence agriculture has the same priority as land demand for monetized economic processes within the global economy.
<i>Land protection</i>	Protection of 20% of primary forest	Protection of 30% of primary forest.
<i>Target subsistence land intensity</i>	Model default.	
<i>Maximum land conversion rate</i>	Low: 0.004.	
<i>Climate related assumptions</i>	No climate damages, no climate feedbacks.	

Table 2: Scenario parametrization for Green growth (GG) and Degrowth (DG).

S3 Sensitivity tests

Test design

Since we find that the DG scenario performs better than the GG scenario in terms of planetary boundary indicators, the sensitivity tests aim to test the consequences of a possible overestimation of DG related intensity improvement factors and a possible underestimation of GG related improvement factors. Table 3 lists the changes made in the sensitivity tests (ST) for GG and DG.

Variable	ST1: Optimistic GG	ST2: Pessimistic DG
<i>Energy intensity</i>	Original value for energy intensity reductions due to electrification multiplied by 1.5.	Original value for energy intensity reductions due to higher labor intensity multiplied by 0.5.
<i>Land intensity of energy generation</i>	Original value multiplied by 1.5.	Original value multiplied by 0.5.
<i>Greenhouse gas emission intensity of N2O and CH4</i>	Instead of a constant value, intensity is reduced by 20%.	Original values for emission intensity reduction multiplied by 0.75.
<i>N and P pollution intensity of agriculture</i>	Instead of a constant value, intensity is reduced by 20%.	Original value multiplied by 0.75.
<i>Blue water intensity</i>	Only 50% of green water reductions are substituted by blue water.	No changes to original value.
<i>Organic agriculture factor</i>	-	Factor increases by 25%, i.e. greater increase in land intensity due to organic agriculture.
<i>Plant-based diet factor</i>	-	Factor increases by 25%, i.e. less land intensity improvements due to plant-based diet.

Table 3: Parameter changes in sensitivity tests.

Test results

- Biosphere integrity: No changes in general dynamics but the index value rises higher and declines slower in the DG scenario.
- Land system change: The index in the DG scenario does not decline but increases slightly and then remains constant. The GG scenario outperforms the DG scenario earlier in the simulation (from 2050 onwards). However, there are no significant differences in the final result; in both scenarios, the index stays between the upper and lower thresholds.
- Radiative forcing: No changes in general dynamics.
- CO2 concentration: No changes in general dynamics.
- Ocean acidification: No changes in general dynamics
- Biogeochemical (N) flows: No changes in general dynamics.
- Biogeochemical (N) flows: No changes in general dynamics but the index value declines slower in the DG scenario and does not fall below the upper or lower threshold value until the end of the simulation.
- Novel entities: No changes in general dynamics although the index value increases slower in this version of the DG scenario than in the original version.
- Aerosol loading: No changes in general dynamics although the index value increases slower in this version of the DG scenario than in the original version.
- Blue & green water: No changes in general dynamics.

Graphical visualization of the evolution of the Planetary Boundary Indicators (PBIs) in ST1 and ST2.